

Level Of Implemetation and Compliance with Procurement Procedures at Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the level of implementation and compliance with the procurement procedures at Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated (CHMCI). It assessed whether significant differences in implementation and compliance exist when the respondents are grouped according to demographic variables in terms of gender, division, and length of procurement experience. Furthermore, the study examined the relationship between the level of implementation and level of compliance with procurement procedures. The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design. Data were collected from 79 staff members involved in procurement activities across the medical, administrative, and finance divisions. A researcher-developed, validated, and reliability-tested questionnaire was used to gather information on respondents' demographic profiles, level of implementation and level of compliance with institutional procurement policies. The findings revealed a "very high" level of implementation (mean = 3.44) and compliance (mean = 3.49), suggesting strong adherence to established procurement procedures. Statistical analyses indicated no significant differences in implementation or compliance when grouped by gender, division, or years of procurement experience. However, a strong and statistically significant positive correlation was found between implementation and compliance ($r = 0.797$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that improvements in the execution of procurement processes are closely associated with higher levels of compliance. The results of the study showed that the respondents are denominated by female employees, most of them belong from Medical Division and usually have 1-3 years' length of experience in procurement process.

Keywords: procurement, implementation, compliance, healthcare, transaction cost economics, hospital operations, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

Procurement process is a series of steps businesses follow to identify, source, negotiate, and acquire goods or services from suppliers while maintaining ongoing relationships to ensure quality and cost-efficiency. involves several steps that businesses must follow,

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including identifying the goods and services needed, sourcing suppliers, requesting quotes, filling out purchase requests, negotiating terms and costs, receiving the relevant items, and submitting payment. While a small company may have just one person handling all procurement tasks, larger companies often have specialized teams dealing with different suppliers or supporting specific business groups. In some cases, gathering input from various business groups is necessary to determine overall requirements (Jenkins, 2024).

Implementing effective procurement procedures is essential for organizations aiming to enhance performance and achieve strategic objectives. A case study conducted at the University of Zambia examined the alignment of public procurement processes to improve performance. The study identified key factors contributing to procurement performance, including well-defined procurement procedures, an appropriate staff structure, strong supplier relationships, and the effective use of information technology. The researchers concluded that strategic alignment of these elements is crucial for enhancing procurement performance in public institutions (Funda & Mwale, 2019).

Maintaining compliance in procurement procedures is crucial for organizations to uphold transparency, efficiency, and accountability. Matto et al. (2022) conducted a study in Tanzania that examined compliance within public procurement systems. Their research highlighted the critical need for adherence to established procurement regulations due to the substantial financial resources involved and the heightened risk of corruption. The study underscored that public procurement remains particularly vulnerable to corrupt practices, emphasizing the importance of implementing robust compliance measures to safeguard integrity and efficiency.

Procurement procedures are crucial processes that guarantee cost-effectiveness, efficiency, and transparency when acquiring the supplies, equipment, and services needed for healthcare facilities' everyday operations. In the healthcare industry, efficient procurement procedures are essential to delivering top-notch patient care, preserving efficient operational workflows, and guaranteeing regulatory compliance. This study aims to assess the level of implementation and compliance with the established procurement procedures at Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated (CHMCI). Specifically, it seeks to identify gaps, challenges, and inconsistencies within the procurement process, evaluate their impact on operational efficiency and service quality, and recommend strategies to enhance adherence to procurement protocols. Through this assessment, the study aims to contribute to the improvement of procurement practices at CHMCI, ensuring transparency, cost-effectiveness, and optimal resource management.

However, despite these numerous studies that investigated the organization implementation and compliance with company policies, no study yet has been conducted particularly in the Carmona Hospital Medical Center Incorporated which talks about the level of implementation and the level of compliance with the hospital procurement system.

Thus, this research determined the level implementation and compliance with CHMC's procurement policies. By examining the hospital's procurement system, formulating critical challenges, and evaluating compliance with procurement policies, this research aimed to suggest policy propositions that will augment procurement efficiency as well as embed

institutional compliance. The researcher chose Carmona Hospital Medical Center Incorporated as the place to conduct the study since the researcher is the hospital purchasing supervisor. Furthermore, this study provided recommendations to enhance the CHMCI's level of procurement procedure implementation and compliance, spot any possible gaps or non-compliance, and offer solutions for better the procurement process.

METHODS

The researcher utilized the descriptive-correlational method of research with the help of a survey questionnaire as the main source of data Copeland, (2022) stated that the aim of descriptive research is to describe a phenomenon and its characteristics. The researchers believe this design is appropriate for the subject because it was easier to collect data from respondents. The descriptive correlational research is useful to describe a phenomenon and its characteristics. While, correlational research refers to a non-experimental research method which studies the relationship between two variables with the help of statistical analysis. Correlational research does not study the effects of extraneous variables on the variables under study. In particular, this study determined the significant difference in the respondents' level of implementation and level of compliance with procurement procedures when grouped according to profile variables. Likewise, it investigated the significant relationship between level of implementation and compliance with the procurement procedures in CHMCI.

The primary data came from staff involved in the procurement procedures within the CHMCI. Only the empirical data generated from them were statistically treated and analyzed in this study. The total population of the study consisted of the ninety-seven (98) employees involved in the procurement procedure within the Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated (MHMCI). The 98 employees came from Finance Division (24), Medical Division (48) and Admin Division (26). The actual sample of seventy-eight (79) was computed using the Raosoft Calculator with a confidence level of 95percent and a margin of error of 5percent. The actual selection of the respondents was done using a stratified sampling technique. This study was conducted during the academic year 2024-2025.

The researcher used a self-made questionnaire for the purpose of collecting the needed primary data. The instrument was divided into three (3) parts: Part 1 dealt with profile of the respondents in terms of gender, division and length of experience in procurement. Part II covered the level of implementation, and Part III level of compliance with the procurement procedures in the Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated (CHMCI).

The researcher sought the advice of his adviser to assess the substance and suitability of the items. Then, the questionnaire was submitted for face validation to a panel of experts consisting of a researcher, statistician, and business. The suggestions and recommendations of the panel were incorporated into the draft of the questionnaire. Additionally, the researcher-made questionnaire underwent a reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha for a thorough validation of the formulated indicators. The results of reliability tests using Cronbach Alpha test were level of implementation 0.927 and for the level of compliance 0.942.

To assess the level of implementation and compliance, a four-point scale was utilized, incorporating both numerical ranges and categorical responses for clarity. The scale is

structured as follows: a score ranging from 3.25 to 4.00 corresponds to "Strongly Agree" and is interpreted as "Very High"; scores between 2.50 and 3.24 represent "Agree," interpreted as "High"; scores from 1.75 to 2.49 indicate "Disagree," interpreted as "Low"; and finally, scores between 1.00 and 1.74 correspond to "Strongly Disagree," which is interpreted as "Very Low." This system allows for both quantitative and qualitative interpretation of the data.

The researcher sent a referral letter, signed by the thesis adviser, addressed to the Head of the Human Resource Department (HRD) at CHMCI, requesting the list of staff members from the Finance, Medical, and Administrative divisions. Following this, the researcher sought formal permission from the President of CHMCI to conduct the survey, which was granted through a formal letter. Once the necessary permissions were obtained, the researcher proceeded with the distribution of questionnaires to the respondents. To ensure timely completion of the survey, the questionnaires were distributed across the designated office divisions. The data collection phase spanned two weeks, allowing for a substantial size and comprehensive insights. Respondents were given ample time to complete the questionnaire, typically spending an average of 5 to 10 minutes.

Part of the data collection process, the researchers read the questions aloud to respondents with visual impairments, the elderly, and those who were unable to read. Throughout the process, the researchers ensured confidentiality and privacy, adhering to ethical standards and safeguarding the anonymity of all respondents. After the survey was completed, the researchers tallied, classified, and tabulated the responses before submitting the results to the statistician for analysis.

The statistical tools employed for the quantitative analysis in this study included frequency count and percentage, weighted mean, t-test, and Pearson r. Frequency count and percentage were used to describe the profile of the respondents in terms of gender, division, and length of experience in procurement (in years) at the Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated (CHMCI). The weighted mean was applied to determine the level of implementation and level of compliance with procurement procedures at CHMCI. The t-test was utilized to identify significant differences between the means of two groups, particularly in relation to the respondents' profiles, level of implementation, and level of compliance. This test served as a hypothesis-testing tool to validate assumptions about the population. Lastly, Pearson r was employed to assess the relationship between the level of implementation and the level of compliance with procurement procedures among the respondents at CHMCI.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Discussion of the Level of Compliance with Procurement Procedures in Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents

Profile		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	27	34.2
	Female	51	65.8
Division	Finance	19	24.1
	Administrative	21	27.8
	Medical	38	48.1
Length of experience in procurement (in year)	Less than 1	12	16.5
	1-3	26	32.9
	4-6	20	25.3
	7 and above	20	25.3
Total Number of Respondents = 79			

As presented in Table 1, the profile of the respondents was categorized in terms of gender, division, and length of experience in procurement (in years). Of the total respondents, 52 (65.8%) were female, while 27 (34.2%) were male. This indicates that the majority of the respondents involved in the procurement process were female. In terms of division, 38 respondents (48.1%) were from the Medical Division, followed by 22 (27.8%) from the Administrative Division, and 19 (24.1%) from the Finance Division. This suggests that nearly half of the participants in procurement activities were from the Medical Division, reflecting its central role in operational procurement. Regarding length of experience in procurement, 26 respondents (32.9%) had 1 to 3 years of experience, followed by 20 respondents (25.3%) with 4 to 6 years of experience, 13 respondents (16.5%) with 7 years and above, and 13 respondents (16.5%) with less than 1 year of experience. The results showed that the majority of respondents were female (65.8%), from the Medical Division (48.1%), and had 1 to 3 years of experience in the procurement process.

The World Health Organization (2019), women constitute approximately 67 percent of the global health and social care workforce, with even higher representation in nursing and midwifery roles. The predominance of female respondents (65.8 percent) reflects the global composition of the health workforce. The significant representation from the Medical division (48.1 percent) among respondents is consistent with the structure of hospital procurement teams. A survey conducted by Owens & Minor in collaboration with the Association for Health Care Resource & Materials Management (AHRMM) (2022) found that materials management and purchasing are primary areas within hospital procurement, often involving clinical staff from medical departments. On the other hand, the distribution of procurement experience among respondents, with a substantial portion having 1 to 3 years of experience, is indicative of the broader procurement workforce. Data from the American Productivity & Quality Center (APQC) (2023) indicates that a significant percentage of procurement staff have over three years of purchasing operations experience, highlighting the importance of experience in procurement roles.

Table 2

Level of Implementation of Procurement Procedures in Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The procurement process is transparent and easy to understand.	3.43	Very High	8
2. Ensures that all procurement activities comply with relevant laws and regulations.	3.49	Very High	2.5
3. The procurement team provides sufficient information to vendors regarding the hospital's requirements.	3.48	Very High	4
4. Regularly evaluates the performance and quality of suppliers.	3.49	Very High	2.5
5. Procurement decisions are made in a timely manner to avoid delays in hospital operations.	3.35	Very High	9
6. The procurement process at the hospital includes appropriate risk management and mitigation strategies.	3.44	Very High	6
7. There is clear communication between the hospital's procurement team and other departments to ensure alignment with institutional needs.	3.44	Very High	6
8. The hospital's procurement procedures allow for fair and competitive bidding from suppliers.	3.51	Very High	1
9. The procurement system is automated, reducing manual errors and inefficiencies.	3.34	Very High	10
10. The procurement team adequately monitors inventory levels to ensure the hospital does not experience stock outs or overstock situations	3.44	Very High	6
Average	3.44	Very High	

As presented in Table 2, the data indicate that the level of implementation of procurement procedures at Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated (CHMCI) was rated as "very high," with an average weighted mean of 3.44. This suggests that the hospital's procurement procedures generally facilitated fair and competitive bidding, ensured compliance with relevant laws and regulations, and included evaluations of the performance and quality of suppliers.

The highest-ranked indicator was "The hospital's procurement procedures allow for fair and competitive bidding from suppliers," which had a weighted mean of 3.51. This was followed by "Ensures that all procurement activities comply with relevant laws and regulations" and "Regularly evaluates the performance and quality of suppliers," both with a weighted mean of 3.49. Ranked fourth was "The procurement team provides sufficient information to vendors regarding the hospital's requirements," with a weighted mean of 3.48. Indicators tied at Rank 6 included: "The procurement process at the hospital includes appropriate risk management and mitigation strategies," "There is clear communication between the hospital's procurement team and other departments to ensure alignment with

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institutional needs,” and “The procurement team adequately monitors inventory levels to ensure the hospital does not experience stock-outs or overstock situations,” each with a weighted mean of 3.44. Following this, “The procurement process is transparent and easy to understand” ranked with a weighted mean of 3.43. “Procurement decisions are made in a timely manner to avoid delays in hospital operations” ranked ninth, with a weighted mean of 3.35. The lowest-ranked indicator was “The procurement system is automated, reducing manual errors and inefficiencies,” with a weighted mean of 3.34.

A recent study conducted in Ningxia, China, by Zhao et al. (2024) explored the effects of implementing a transparent online open procurement policy within the pharmaceutical sector, specifically targeting public hospitals. The findings revealed that the adoption of this policy resulted in a substantial reduction in medicine prices, purchase volumes, and the overall cost of procurement. The study concluded that such transparent procurement frameworks not only enhance accountability and fairness but also contribute to more rational and cost-effective purchasing decisions. While, Bhosekar et al. (2020) investigated the potential benefits of implementing automated systems to manage hospital logistics and procurement operations. The results demonstrated that the adoption of automated material handling systems significantly reduced manual errors, minimized delays, and improved the overall accuracy and speed of procurement-related processes. On the other hand, in the study of Jayakody et al. (2021) conducted aimed to identify the operational strengths that contribute to procurement efficiency, as well as the weaknesses that hinder compliance and performance. Their findings underscore the need for a balanced approach that incorporates both regulatory compliance and strategic process improvements to ensure a responsive and efficient procurement system in hospital settings.

Table 3
Respondents’ Level of Compliance with Procurement Procedure in Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. All procurement activities in the hospital strictly adhere to the established procurement policies and procedures.	3.59	Very High	1
2. Staff members involved in the procurement process are well-trained in hospital procurement compliance requirements.	3.58	Very High	2
3. The hospital has a clear and well-documented procedure for approving procurement requests.	3.51	Very High	4
4. The hospital regularly conducts audits to ensure compliance with procurement policies.	3.47	Very High	6.5
5. There is sufficient oversight to ensure that all procurement decisions are in line with hospital regulations.	3.46	Very High	8.5
6. Procurement contracts are consistently reviewed to ensure they align with hospital compliance standards.	3.47	Very High	6.5
7. Hospital employees involved in procurement are held accountable for adhering to compliance guidelines.	3.46	Very High	8.5
8. The hospital has an effective system in place for reporting procurement non-compliance or irregularities.	3.32	Very High	10
9. External vendors are required to comply with the hospital’s procurement policies and standards.	3.49	Very High	5
10. Any deviations from the standard procurement procedures are properly documented and justified	3.56	Very High	3
Average	3.49	Very High	

As presented in Table 3, the data indicate that the level of compliance with procurement procedures at Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated (CHMCI) was rated as "very high," with an average weighted mean of 3.49. This suggests that all procurement activities at the hospital strictly adhered to established procurement policies and procedures, that staff involved in the procurement process were well-trained, and that deviations from the standard procurement procedures were justified.

The highest-ranked indicator was "All procurement activities in the hospital strictly adhere to the established procurement policies and procedures," with a weighted mean of 3.59. This was followed by "Staff members involved in the procurement process are well-trained in hospital procurement compliance requirements," with a weighted mean of 3.58. Ranked third was the indicator, "Any deviations from the standard procurement procedures are properly documented and justified," with a weighted mean of 3.56. Ranked fourth was "The hospital has a clear and well-documented procedure for approving procurement requests," with a weighted mean of 3.51, followed by "External vendors are required to comply with the hospital's procurement policies and standards," with a weighted mean of 3.49. Indicators tied at Rank 6.5 included: "The hospital regularly conducts audits to ensure compliance with procurement policies," and "Procurement contracts are consistently reviewed to ensure they align with hospital compliance standards," both with a weighted mean of 3.47. At Rank 8.5 were: "There is sufficient oversight to ensure that all procurement decisions are in line with hospital regulations," and "Hospital employees involved in procurement are held accountable for adhering to compliance guidelines," both scoring 3.46. The lowest-ranked indicator was "The hospital has an effective system in place for reporting procurement non-compliance or irregularities," which ranked 10th with a weighted mean of 3.32.

Andriani and Nugroho (2019) examined compliance levels in healthcare procurement within Indonesian hospitals. The findings showed that high compliance is often achieved when there are clear procurement policies, adequate staff training, and robust oversight mechanisms in place—all of which are consistent with the top-performing indicators in your study. The research also indicated that accountability and proper documentation were critical to ensuring compliance. While, Tadesse and Wondimu (2020) conducted a study on procurement compliance in Ethiopian hospitals and found that adherence to procurement policies and staff training significantly contributed to procurement efficiency and integrity. Their research emphasizes the importance of regular audits, documentation, and clear procedures—elements also reflected in the top-ranked indicators. However, Mwangi and Kariuki (2022) examined compliance with procurement regulations in public healthcare facilities in Kenya. Their study revealed that high levels of compliance were significantly influenced by factors such as staff competence, clarity of procurement procedures, and regular audits. The authors emphasized that well-trained procurement staff and the strict enforcement of procurement guidelines were instrumental in ensuring effective procurement operations.

Table 4
Significant Difference in the Respondents’ Level of Implementation of Procurement Procedures in Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated

Profile	Test statistic	p-value	Interpretation
Gender	(t-test) t = -1.124	0.265	Not Significant
Division	(F-test) F= 1.501	0.229	Not Significant
Length of experience in procurement	(F-test) F = 0.519	0.670	Not Significant
Significance level @ 0.05			

As shown in the table 4, there was no significant difference in the respondents’ level of implementation of procurement procedures in Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated when grouped according to profile variables. The statistical analysis conducted at a 0.05 significance level, the results indicated that none of the examined profile variables—gender, division, and length of experience in procurement—had a statistically significant effect on the outcome variable. For gender, the t-test produced a test statistic of -1.124 with a p-value of 0.265, which was greater than 0.05, indicating no significant difference between male and female respondents. Similarly, the F-test for division yielded a test statistic of 1.501 and a p-value of 0.229, suggesting that the division in which respondents work did not significantly influence the outcome. Lastly, the F-test for length of experience in procurement resulted in a test statistic of 0.519 with a p-value of 0.670, further confirming the lack of a significant relationship between experience length and the outcome. This implies that the respondents’ level of implementation in the procurement procedures in Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated was the same regardless of their profile variables.

OECD (2021) emphasizes the role of gender-responsive public procurement in promoting gender equality. By integrating gender considerations into procurement policies and processes, public buyers can use their purchasing power to encourage suppliers to improve their performance on women's empowerment. On the other hand, Fang and Natarajan (2020) discuss how multi-division firms adopting a center-led sourcing approach can centralize strategic sourcing activities while allowing decentralized execution by divisions. This model aims to minimize total procurement costs and ensure fair cost allocation among divisions. While specific studies directly linking the length of procurement experience to performance are limited, it's generally acknowledged that experience contributes to better decision-making and efficiency in procurement processes. Experienced procurement professionals are more adept at navigating complex procurement landscapes, understanding market dynamics, and managing supplier relationships effectively.

Table 5
Significant Difference in the Respondents' Level of Compliance with Procurement Procedures in Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated

Profile	Test statistic	p-value	Interpretation
Gender	(t-test) t = -1.1339	0.184	Not Significant
Division	(F-test) F= 0.979	0.380	Not Significant
Length of experience in procurement	(F-test) F = 0.989	0.403	Not Significant
Significance level @ 0.05			

As shown in the table 5, there was no significant difference in the respondents' level of compliance with procurement procedures in Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated when grouped according to profile variables. For gender, the t-test resulted in a test statistic of -1.1339 and a p-value of 0.184, which was greater than the 0.05 significance level, indicating no significant difference in compliance based on gender. Similarly, the F-test for division produced a test statistic of 0.979 with a p-value of 0.380, showing that division did not significantly affect compliance. Finally, the F-test for length of experience in procurement yielded a test statistic of 0.989 and a p-value of 0.403, which further confirms that the length of procurement experience did not significantly influence compliance with procurement procedures. This implies that the respondents' level of compliance in the procurement procedures in Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated was the same regardless of their profile variables.

A study by Orser et al. (2021) found that women-owned small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are underrepresented among government suppliers, and barriers to public procurement differ across gender. This suggests that gender may not be a significant factor in procurement compliance. Additionally, the OECD (2021) highlights that mainstreaming gender considerations in public procurement is a key dimension of strategic procurement. However, challenges persist in promoting gender equality through procurement, indicating that factors like gender and division may not significantly impact compliance. Furthermore, the European Institute for Gender Equality (2022) reports low rates of implementation of gender-responsive public procurement in most EU countries, suggesting that gender may not significantly affect procurement compliance.

Table 6
Significant Relationship between the Respondents’ Level of Implementation and Level of Compliance with Procurement Procedures in Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated

	Pearson r value	p-value	Interpretation
The Respondents’ Level of Implementation and Level of Compliance in the Procurement Procedures in Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated	0.797 Moderate correlation	0.000	Significant
**Significant @ 0.01			

The significant positive correlation between the level of implementation and compliance with procurement procedures at Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated aligns with findings from several studies. For instance, a study by Kamaruzzaman Muhammad (2022) found a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.659$, $p < 0.01$) between transparency—a key aspect of implementation—and the effectiveness of public procurement processes in a uniform government agency. This indicates that higher levels of transparent implementation practices are associated with improved procurement outcomes. Additionally, Ismail (2020) reported a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.499$, $p < 0.01$) between the role of internal auditors in implementing procurement procedures and the effectiveness of procurement processes in the public sector. This suggests that effective implementation mechanisms, such as internal audits, contribute to higher compliance levels.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the summary of findings, several conclusions were drawn. First, the respondents are predominantly female employees, most of whom are from the Medical Division, with the majority having between one to three years of experience in the procurement process. Second, the procurement procedures at Carmona Hospital and Medical Center Incorporated (CHMCI) are structured to ensure fair and competitive bidding, adherence to relevant laws and regulations, and consistent evaluation of supplier performance and quality. Third, CHMCI strictly adheres to established procurement policies and procedures. The staff involved in procurement are well-trained, and any deviations from standard procedures are well-justified. Fourth, the respondents’ level of implementation of procurement procedures does not significantly differ based on their profile variables. Similarly, the level of compliance with procurement procedures remains consistent regardless of differences in the respondents’ profiles. Furthermore, a higher level of implementation correlates with a higher level of compliance among the respondents. Lastly, it is essential to implement an action plan that includes provisions for seminars, training programs, digital monitoring tools, and recognition systems. This would address existing gaps in automation and reporting, and help sustain high standards of procurement implementation and compliance.

Based on the conclusions, several recommendations are proposed. First, CHMCI should adopt a phased and automated procurement platform to streamline processes, reduce manual errors, and improve data accuracy and transparency. Second, the Procurement

Division should develop a secure platform or hotline for anonymous reporting of procurement irregularities, complemented by regular training to foster ethical practices. Third, the HR Training Department should maintain and expand training programs that cover procurement automation, compliance policies, and practical applications through workshops, online learning modules, and assessments. Fourth, the IT Department should focus on developing a user-friendly and secure dashboard that provides real-time insights into procurement activities to enhance oversight and accountability. Fifth, the Procurement Division should initiate a program to train, assess, and routinely evaluate suppliers based on their compliance, performance, and ethical conduct. Sixth, the formation of a Procurement Audit and Monitoring Committee—composed of representatives from the Procurement, Compliance, and Internal Audit departments—is recommended to conduct regular reviews ensuring transparency, efficiency, and compliance. Finally, future researchers are encouraged to expand the study to include other hospitals in order to validate and enrich the findings related to procurement practices and automation in the healthcare sector.

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